

ISLAMIC EDUCATION LEARNING DESIGN BASED ON "SISTEM AMONG"

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ABSTRACT

Today, the Islamic education learning design tends teacher centered so the end result only transfer of knowledge. One learning design that can be applied in teaching of Islamic education is Sistem Among. Sistem Among created by Ki Hajar Dewantara an education system which is implemented by providing the freedom for students to act freely based on the rules, including the Quran and Hadith. So, the system can develop a sense of confidence, aspirations and activities of students. Sistem Among consists of three principles, That is *nontoni* (observe), *niteni* (recall/memorize), and *nirokaken* (*imitated*). Sistem Among aims to build students to be faithful and devoted man, physically and spiritually independent, virtuous, intelligent and skilled, physically and mentally healthy, to become a good citizenship, responsible for religion, and welfare homeland. The formulation of the problem to be discussed is how to design of Islamic education learning with Sistem Among. Three basic principles of Sistem Among require active participation and appreciative of teachers in Islamic education. Thus, This system is expected to bring forth a superior muslim, competent, and able to actualize the values of Islam *rahmatan lil Alamin*.

Keywords: Learning Design, Islam, Islamic Education, Sistem Among

ABSTRAK

Dewasa ini, desain pendidikan agama Islam cenderung teacher centered sehingga hasil akhir berupa *transfer of knowlegde* semata. Salah satu desain pembelajaran yang bisa diterapkan dalam pembelajaran PAI adalah Sistem Among. Sistem Among digagas oleh Ki Hajar Dewantara, merupakan sistem pendidikan yang dilaksanakan dengan memberikan kebebasan kepada peserta didik untuk bertindak leluasa asalkan sesuai dengan aturan, termasuk Quran dan Hadis. sehingga, sistem ini dapat menumbuhkan rasa percaya diri, aspirasi, dan aktivitas peserta didik. Sistem Among terdiri dari tiga prinsip, yaitu: *nontoni* (melihat), *niteni* (mengingat), dan *nirokaken* (meniru). Sistem among bertujuan untuk membangun peserta didik menjadi manusia beriman dan bertaqwa, merdeka lahir batin, berbudi luhur, cerdas dan berketerampilan, serta sehat jasmani dan rohani agar menjadi anggota masyarakat yang baik, bertanggung jawab atas agama, dan kesejahteraan tanah air. Rumusan masalah yang akan dibahas adalah bagaimana desain pembelajaran pendidikan agama Islam dengan Sistem Among. Tiga prinsip dasar sistem among menuntut peran aktif dan apresiatif guru PAI. Sistem ini diharapkan melahirkan pribadi muslim yang unggul, kompeten serta mampu mengaktualisasikan nilai-nilai Islam *rahmatan lil alamin*.

Kata Kunci: Desain Pembelajaran, Islam, Pendidikan Agama Islam, Sistem Among

A. INTRODUCTION

Today, the Islamic education learning design tends teacher-centered so the end result only transfer of knowledge. Whereas in Indonesia, learning design embraces two curriculum (KTSP and Kurikulum 2013) are demanding student-centered learning. According Mahfudin (2013: 154), KTSP was developed based on the Law of National Education System Number 20 Year 2003 (UU Sisdiknas 2013) with the following principles: 1) centered on the needs and interests of students; 2) varied and integrated; 3) responsive to development of science and technology; 4) relevant with needs of life; 5) comprehensive and continuous; 6) lifelong learning (life long education); 7) balance between national interests and regional interests. so in Kurikulum 2013, learning more emphasis on involvement of student to grow their potential (Mayasari, 2014: 13). from two curriculum, it seems that learning requires active role in students. So that teachers act as facilitators in the learning process leads students to active for achieve the learning objectives, including the Islamic education learning in high school.

Islamic Education as a coaching lesson for religious and morality aspect are expected to produce muslims generation who were cognitively intelligent, moral, and social (Syahidin, 2014: 12). In reality, Learning of Islamic Education in high school is not made to increase cognitively knowledge be meaning and value. Islamic education rated not educate comprehensively, providing all aspects of competency in a balanced way, but tends to teach and make up ability in memorize and complete the exams only (Abduh, 2015). Students lacking or not able to sense, appreciate and apply the moral values taught in schools (Putra & Lisnawati, 2012: 11). Buchori (1992) adds failure of Islamic education learning is caused educational practice were attentive to cognitive aspects of religious values and ignore to coaching aspect of affective and conative-volitive, such as the willingness and determination to practice the values of religious teaching. These conditions make a gap between knowledge and practice. This fact was agreed by Basuni (2004) that Islamic education tends to emphasize the cognitive aspect (thinking) rather than affective (taste) and psychomotor (behavior).

So, studying as a process of Islamic education did not attract for students, this is caused by the various components in the Islamic education learning itself. From various highlights which presented by experts of education, looks problematic in Islamic Education learning lies on the question is how Islamic education learning design is not limited to the aspects of knowledge but able to provide inspiration and practice (Choiri & Fitriani, 2011: 310). It is caused the success educating students in learning of Islamic education isn't only measured in the value with numerical symbol, but success of transforming the Islamic and moral values to their students. Here, exemplary and morality of teacher will largely determine the success of learning of Islamic education (Sahniar, 2016).

Teacher as a figure who respected and emulated should provide exemplary students. It has long been suggested by the great thinkers of education in Indonesia, Ki Hajar Dewantara through model of Sistem Among. Concept of the model include a principle that students is seen as subject who have an important position; students have freedom in accordance with the nature; there should be no compulsion in the learning process; learning occurs in a pleasant conditions; teacher should appreciate anything of students; and learning is meant to instill good character (Subandiyah, 2012: 3).

The principles of Sistem Among can be applied to designing Islamic education learning in global era. Aligned with one of Strategic Plan from Ministry of Education

and Culture (Kemendikbud) on the Plan of National Long-Term Development (RPJPN) 2005-2025 about "Identity and National Character". Strengthening identity and national character through Sistem Among in Islamic education learning is expected to support nawacita of Jokowi-Jusuf Kalla who want to revolutionize the national character, strengthen diversity and strengthen social restoration in Indonesia (Kemendikbud, 2015).

Sistem Among consider any activities should be done by students. Islamic education learning process with Sistem Among is designed to adjust the students through nontoni (observe), niteni (memorize, recall), and nirokaken (imitate). Through three stages are expected of Islamic education may bring unpleasant impression for students. In addition, the development of self-confidence, aspirations, and activities of students expected to bring character as a human being faithful and devoted, independent inner and outer, virtuous, intelligent and skilled, as well as physically and mentally healthy in order to become a member of the good citizenship, responsible of religion, and the welfare of the homeland. So expectations of Islamic education in giving birth muslims generation are superior, competent and able to actualize the values of Islam rahmatan lil alamin.

B. RESEARCH METODHS

The study used a qualitative approach in the process of collecting and processing data. A qualitative approach is methodology to investigating the phenomenon of social and human problems. Bogdan & Taylor (in Moleong, 2008: 3) argue that qualitative approach is a procedure who produces descriptive data in the form of words written or spoken of phenomena observed. So, excavation efforts in the application of the Sistem Among on Islamic education learning in high schools assessed with the help of the literature such as books and journals, research reports, and other relevant literature. The purpose of writing to be discussed is exposure of the Islamic education learning design with Sistem Among.

Analysis methods with literature reviews. it can be conducted by investigating all data obtained from documents, records, files, and other things that have been documented and proven reliability. One of the advantages of this method is easy to replace reference because the data source are fixed. To making documentations guide are containing guidelines outlines the data helped facilitate with assessment framework to applied in paper (Djauhary, 2013).

To support the above statement, research was conducted in SMA Negeri 1 Babakan and SMK Negeri 12 Bandung. After observing the implementation of the Islamic education learning in the classroom and interviews with Islamic education teachers, some things were found: (1) teacher is not able to develop a lesson plan (RPP) PAI, especially for young teachers; (2) teacher is not able to choose compatible learning materials; (3) teacher tend to use monotone technique (exp. discourse); (4) teacher rely on textbooks from government as the main teaching materials; (5) the teacher is not able to create innovations with a variety of media, (6) assessment is carried out only to measure students cognitive aspects. (7) lowness Islamic literacy, so required extra energy for teaching (especially in reading and understanding the Quran), (8) habituation of Islamic behavior is still low.

C. LITERATUR REVIEW

1. Sistem Among

The term *among* is derived from the Javanese word meaning 'care', *momong* means 'nurturing' and *pamong* means 'nanny' (Kamus Besar Bahasa Jawa, 2002). The word *momong*, *among*, and *ngemong* has the same meaning that is 'care', 'nurturing', and 'nanny'. *Sistem Among* is one of the educational model in Tamansiswa proposed by Ki Hajar Dewantara since 1922. However, people are more familiar with the term *tut wuri handayani*. In Great Regulations and Charter of Tamansiswa Chapter IV on 12th article, *Sistem Among* as an educational model is founded on the foundations of kinship, based on: 1) nature (as a prerequisite for achieving progress in fast and good); and 2) freedom (as a prerequisite for changing and moving inner strength till children have strong personality and be able to think and act independently). In management, *Sistem Among* as known as *paguron* meaning school (Majelis Luhur Persatuan Tamansiswa, 1989: 31).

Spirit of brotherhood in *Sistem Among* is implemented based on love to others, respect and appreciate values of diversity, mutual help, democracy, and as a mean to build unity. Based on the values of freedom and nature, *Sistem Among* gives freedom to students for develop themselves accordance with their character (Hadiwijoyo, et al., 2005: 15).

Sistem Among placing students as the most important aspect in the learning process. Ki Hajar Dewantara refer students as a manifestation that should be appreciated (Subandiyah, 2015: 276). It forbids any coercion in the learning process, although the main objective practicing self-discipline. Because compulsion potentially eliminating the spirit of freedom in education.

The basic purpose of *Sistem Among* to familiarize good manners to students; build a harmonious communication between teachers and students in creating a leader figure (*ngemong*) (Suwignyo, 2009: 8-9). Teachers are expected to encourage motivation and initiative of students when together (*ing madya mangun karsa*), and teachers able to be a role model, mentor, and an example in front of students (*ing ngarsa sung tuladha*) (Surjomihardjo, 1986 in Suwignyo, 2009: 3). It learning process requires teachers to expert in material and skills for students through *nontoni*, *niteni*, and *nirokaken* (observe, remember/recall, and imitate).

2. Islamic Education

Islamic education is an attempt to create and nurture the students to understand many doctrines of Islam as a whole and goal of life, which in turn can practice and make Islam as way of life (Zakiah Darajdat (in Majid & Andayani, 2004: 13). Whereas Joseph Tayar (in Majid & Andayani, 2004: 13) defines Islamic education as a conscious effort the older generation to transfer of experiences, knowledges, competences, and skills to the younger generation to become a person fear Allah. Arifin (1991: 13) also said that Islamic education is the educational system that can give a person's ability to lead his life in accordance with the Islamic visions, because values of Islam have been animating and coloring shades of his personality (Gafar & Jamil, 2003: 37).

So, it can be seen that delivering of Islamic education by teacher and reception by students are corelated think among teacher and students to believing in existence of the doctrines then to understood, internalized and then practiced or applied, but

there also are demands to respect beliefs of others. If look at the purpose of Islamic education accordance with the goal of human life itself, which is reflected in the words of Allah on Surah Az-Zariyat verse 56.

وَمَا خَلَقْتُ الْجِنَّ وَالْإِنْسَ إِلَّا لِيَعْبُدُونِ

“And I did not create the jinn and mankind except to worship Me”

(Q.S Az-Zariat: 56).

Therefore the purpose of Islamic education should be directed to the achievement of final goal, which is to form a human being who always worship to Allah in all aspects on his life (Joseph & Anwar, 1992: 11). Whereas Islamic education in high school level aims to increase confidence, comprehension, appreciation and practice of students about Islam to be human who is faithful and devoted to Allah SWT, and certain noble in personal life, society, nation and state, as well as for continuing education at higher level (Assyidiq, 2015: 16).

D. RESULTS

The study focuses on the urgency of Islamic education in high school level, because in this level on human development is referred to as mid-adolescence with range 15-18 years (Rumini & Sundari, 2004: 53). Teens already behave to get psychological satisfaction and seek identity (Hariyanto, 2011). Related with that, Islamic education learning in high school is expected to provide assistance and strengthen character to forming ideal Muslims personality through selection learning design based on exemplary, such as *Sistem Among*.

As an educational model, *Sistem Among* describes the steps (syntax) are used by teacher in educating students from the beginning to the end of learning. Syntax serves to outline the model or the phase of learning about how education is run (Joyce & Weil, 1992: 16). The education model is the philosophical basis of any overall approach and beliefs about learning, instruction, and content (Bussinger, 2011).

Syntax of Islamic education model with *Sistem Among* include *nontoni*, *niteni*, and *nirokaken*. The meaning of *nontoni* is seeing or observing is modeled by teacher through modeling in front of students. From observing activity, students trying to *niteni* (memorize, recall to understand). After they understand, students try to *nirokaken* or imitate (teacher make self as a model to observed) (Subandiyah, 2015: 275).

Should be noted that imitations activity does not mean that students have a passive attitude because they just do imitations. In this case, imitate is giving an understanding of the model or example shown previously. then, students create something (innovation) in accordance with their creativity. Each student has freedom to do things according for their nature and talent, as long as the accordance rules of the Quran, the Hadith, rules of school and the learning objectives are contained in Plan of Goals Learning (RPP PAI). In honing creativity in students, coercion avoided, which allowed just punishment when students make mistakes. So, collective agreement between teacher and students on Islamic education learning is indispensable.

Wherease student activities, whatever they do should be appreciated by teacher, even teacher should not be oppose to hard, just do recalling only. With this principle, at the same time, students are expected to learn be respect others, including other people's opinions, either verbally or in writing. Here is table 1 that presented description of the Islamic learning design with *Sistem Among*.

Based on the table 1 can be explained that *Sistem Among* make teacher to inculcate Islamic values (*akhlakul karimah*) for students as easily. for illustration, the

Sistem Among model will be applied to the Islamic education in odd semester of 11th grade on basic competencies "Tolerance and Harmony". In applying *nontoni* (observing), during the learning, teacher asking student conditions (including the background), it is important when first time the teacher teaching in the classroom (for example, when the new school year). After knowing some students have different religious background, teacher gives students a choice to stay or not during PAI learning, and teacher must respect the decision.

Tabel 1
Syntax Sample to Apply *Sistem Among* on Islamic Education Learning

Syntax	Student Activities	Teacher Activities
<i>Nontoni</i> (Observe)	Students see (in the sense of observing) an example or model of the observations made by teacher, and not only through the sense of sight, but also through hearing, including a feeling of involvement on observing the model.	Preparing itself as a model for the students and at the same time prepare the other materials (according to destination), for example, pictures / movies, literatures, including behavior in front of students.
<i>Niteni</i> (Memorize/Recall)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students memorize / recall (record) model or example. For example, with a note to understand the characteristics of the model. Notes obtained from <i>nontoni</i>, or just rely on memory skills of students. • Students discuss the results of their observations with teachers. • Students give input. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide opportunities for students to find all necessary information to understand the model were observed. • Provide opportunities for students to discuss who gets.
<i>Nirokaken</i> (Imitate)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students imitate an observed object. • Students are free to move accordance with the talent and knowledge without any coercion, but should obey the rules. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide greater opportunities for students to move accordance with their talents and knowledge. • Provide guidance to students and remind if the students are wrong. • Appreciate the work produced by students.

Knowing there are different students, teacher should be able to appreciate the different students by keeping the oral and actions so as not to hurt their feelings. The teacher gives an example of diversity led to harmony. so, social competence and literacy of teacher play a dominant role in generating exemplary figure for students. Students see

the model, then *niteni* (understanding) the importance of promoting tolerance and harmony among human beings. Both of these processes can't be separated from the process of imitating (*nirokaken*). Students are free to act in maintaining harmony accordance with their creativity, without removing the concept and rules regarding tolerance and harmony in Islam. Thus, in application of *Sistem Among*, pattern of teacher-centered learning can reduce. At the same time demanding teacher creativity in presenting a good model for students and the model is able to be imitated by students.

Based on the illustration, teacher can also learn how the meaning of "freedom" is not always a negative impact on the lives of students. Students forged to know their rights and duties in religion and environment. *Sistem Among* with the three principles can create pattern of communication between teacher and students harmonious. Islamic education teachers as parents for students in school are not only open to giving love, but understand how their role in the Islamic application in daily life of students (Al-Hamd & Hamd, 2011).

E. DISCUSSION

In the process to building character of Indonesian Muslims generation which high competitiveness needs to be supported by the involvement of all stakeholders in the educational ecosystem. As subjects on internalizing values of Islam, Islamic education in Indonesia has a major role to grow the Islamic skills. It is what distinguishes the function and purpose of Islamic education in Indonesia with other countries in the Middle East, Europe and America (Fathoni, 2015).

Amin (2015) explains in European and America countries, Islamic education only as an instrument to creating social cohesion. Whereas in the countries of the Middle East, Islamic education to form a virtuous man. In Indonesia, Islamic education has the goal of both, to create human beings knowledgeable and foster social cohesion (create the balanced of life in the society) and form a virtuous personality on spiritual and moral (Haedari in Fathoni, 2015). In effort to realize this goal, teacher as one of the components in educational ecosystem needs to seek learning design based on exemplary and able to accommodate the noble goal. Because an exemplary could build relationships, improve credibility, and increase the influence (DePorter, in Naim, 2009: 35)

Islam considers that the *Sistem Among* by Ki Hadjar Dewantara aligned or relevant to concept of Islamic education in general, it can be seen from some bases aspect of Ki Hajar to implementing education (Wahyudi, 2013: 116). Three principles in *Sistem Among* can be applied in Islamic education, because it implicitly has in common with the principles of learning in Islam which provide a good model (Asyafah, 2012: 10). The principle of *nontoni* in learning is also contained in Surah Al-Ahzab ayat 21 and Surah Al Mumtahanan verse 4.

لَقَدْ كَانَ لَكُمْ فِي رَسُولِ اللَّهِ أُسْوَةٌ حَسَنَةٌ لِمَنْ كَانَ يَرْجُو اللَّهَ وَالْيَوْمَ الْآخِرَ وَذَكَرَ اللَّهَ كَثِيرًا

“There has certainly been for you in the Messenger of Allah an excellent pattern for anyone whose hope is in Allah and the Last Day and [who] remembers Allah often.” (Q.S. Al-Ahzab: 21)

فَدَكَانَتْ لَكُمْ أُسْوَةٌ حَسَنَةٌ فِي إِبْرَاهِيمَ وَالَّذِينَ مَعَهُ إِذْ قَالُوا لَقَوْمِهِمْ إِنَّا بُرَاءُ مِنْكُمْ وَمِمَّا تَعْبُدُونَ مِنْ دُونِ اللَّهِ كَفَرْنَا بِكُمْ وَبَدَا بَيْنَنَا وَبَيْنَكُمُ الْعَدَاوَةُ وَالْبَغْضَاءُ أَبَدًا حَتَّى تُؤْمِنُوا بِاللَّهِ وَحَدَهُ إِلَّا قَوْلَ إِبْرَاهِيمَ لِأَبِيهِ لَأَسْتَغْفِرَنَّ لَكَ وَمَا أَمْلِكُ لَكَ مِنَ اللَّهِ مِنْ شَيْءٍ رَبَّنَا عَلَيْنِكَ تَوَكَّلْنَا وَإِلَيْكَ أَنْتَبْنَا وَإِلَيْكَ الْمَصِيرُ

"There has already been for you an excellent pattern in Abraham and those with him, when they said to their people, 'Indeed, we are disassociated from you and from whatever you worship other than Allah . We have denied you, and there has appeared between us and you animosity and hatred forever until you believe in Allah alone' except for the saying of Abraham to his father, 'I will surely ask forgiveness for you, but I have not [power to do] for you anything against Allah . Our Lord, upon You we have relied, and to You we have returned, and to You is the destination'." (Q.S. Al-Mumtahanan: 4).

Whereas the principle of *niteni* also harmonious with the principles of education in Islam. *Niteni* mentioned in Surah Al Jatsiyah: 13 and Surah Yunus: 101.

اللَّهُ الَّذِي سَخَّرَ لَكُمُ الْبَحْرَ لِتَجْرِيَ الْفُلُكُ فِيهِ بِأَمْرِهِ وَلِيُنذِرَكُمْ تَشْكُرُونَ

"And He has subjected to you all that is in the heavens and all that is on the earth. It is all a favor and kindness from Him. Indeed there are signs in it for a people who think deeply." (Q.S. Al-Jatsiyah: 13)

قُلْ انظُرُوا مَاذَا فِي السَّمَاوَاتِ وَالْأَرْضِ وَمَا تُغْنِي الْآيَاتُ وَالنُّذُرُ عَنْ قَوْمٍ لَا يُؤْمِنُونَ

"Say, 'Observe what is in the heavens and earth.' But of no avail will be signs or warners to a people who do not believe." (Q.S. Yunus: 101)

Then the principle of *nirokaken* as the last step of the Sistem Among accordance with the principle of encouraging the practice of Islamic learning is contained in Surah Al Saff verse 2-3 (Asyafah, 2012: 10).

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا لِمَ تَقُولُونَ مَا لَا تَفْعَلُونَ (٢) كَبِيرٌ مَقْتًا عِنْدَ اللَّهِ أَنْ تَقُولُوا مَا لَا تَفْعَلُونَ (٣)

"O you who have believed, why do you say what you do not do? Great is hatred in the sight of Allah that you say what you do not do." (Q.S. Al Saff: 2-3)

When view closely, there is a meeting point between Islamic education and Sistem Among. Because learning model with Sistem Among means the Islamic education learning can be carried out openly, lovingly, freely accordance with the rules (the Quran, Hadith, school rules, and norms of decency), and protect students with coolness and comfort of mind in harmony with the principles of education in Islam which create a virtuous and noble human.

Islamic education learning based on Sistem Among require active participation and appreciative from the teacher. Teacher expects to change the style of teaching be student-centered (students as subjects and objects of study), because Sistem Among model seeks out the intimate communication between teacher and students. In addition, application of Sistem Among is a development effort in improving the quality of Islamic education learning appropriate for the Indonesian context. Thus, this model is expected to build muslim are superior, competent, and able to actualize values of Islam rahmatan lil Alamin without forgetting cultures of the homeland.

F. CONCLUSION

Islamic education learning requires an innovation on delivery to students. As the system was initiated by the father of education in Indonesia, Ki Hajar Dewantara. *Sistem Among* has been adapted to the socio-cultural conditions of Indonesia. The principles of *Sistem Among* are *nontoni* (observe), *niteni* (memorize/recall), and *nirokaken* (imitate). These principles can improve the dignity of Islamic education in our country. *Sistem Among* not only serve as a means of character development, but

also improve the quality of education, including Islamic education in Indonesia, and efforts to achieve Islamic education learning model appropriate to Indonesian Context and concept of "think globally act locally". In addition, *Sistem Among* in Islamic education able to create patterns of student-centered learning and make students excited to receiving Islamic education in high school. Thus, Indonesia hopes to give birth Muslims generation are superior, competent and able to actualize the values of *Islam rahmatan lil alamin* able to be realized.

This study is expected to provide inspiration for the development of further educational studies, particularly in the innovation development of Islamic education learning model is patterned Indonesian. The emphasis on the importance of an exemplary teacher figure and giving love to students in application of Islamic values in their life. Likewise, students not only become the object of life, but also as a subject that is able to reach their goal by maintaining and developing the Islamic and social values in society.

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